

Ref.: Ms. PHEN-1258 (Revised version 1)

Title: " Larvicidal activity, biochemical effect, histopathological alteration and biomarker responses induced by *Laurus nobilis* essential oil in *Culex pipiens* (Diptera: Culicidae)"

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Responses to Reviews

Thanks for all comments and suggestions made by the two reviewers. The revised version 1 has been made according to **all issues** mentioned in the reviewers' comments. In detail, a point by point, the responses to the reviewers' comments are as follows (MS with marked changes in blue and green).

Reviewer 1 (marked changes in blue):

Comment: Tables 1 and 2 should be unique.

Response: we merged the table and the table.

Comment: Figure 1 should be supplementary material

Response: we transferred the Figure 1 in supplementary material.

Comment: The authors should correlate the results of Larvicidal activity with the major compounds in the oil (Consider all molecules with $\geq 5\%$ as major compounds). The authors should search the literature for the likely molecular targets of these compounds to improve their discussions.

Response: we correlated the results of larvicidal activity with the major compounds in the oil (Consider all molecules with $\geq 5\%$ as major compounds) (see the last paragraph of Insecticidal activity in Discussion section)

Comment: The following papers address the topic of the manuscript and can enrich its references: doi.org/10.1021/acsomega.9b03157; doi.org/10.3390/separations11040097; doi.org/10.3390/molecules26237359

Response: we added these papers

Comment: The authors mixed the results and discussions inappropriately. For some data there was good discussion, while for others there was only the writing of the results. I strongly suggest that the authors restructure the manuscript, including a section only for results and another only for discussion of the results. The results section should be divided into subsections, the same should be true for discussions.

Response: The manuscript has been restructured, and the sections 'insecticidal activity' and 'histopathological analysis' have been enhanced with additional references.

Comment: In figures 4 and 5, the authors should include a scale. The scale should be the same for each group of figures.

Response: we included the scale.

Reviewer 2 (marked changes in green):

Comment: Long and complex sentences should be edited to improve fluency and comprehensibility. There should be no imperative sentences.

Response: we edited the long and complex sentences.

Comment: The full name of the words in the text should be added before the first abbreviation. In all subsequent sentences, only abbreviations should be used.

Response: we rectified

Comment: The manuscript does not present numbered lines. Thus, probably it will be difficult for the authors to review the manuscript.

Response: We numbered the lines.

Comment: Abstract and text

It is necessary to express the full name and then use the abbreviation. The full term should be written out upon first, followed by the abbreviation in parentheses. After that, the abbreviation can be used alone. We written the full term

Response: we rectified

Comment: Introduction

In the last paragraph, a sentence emphasizing the originality of the work should be added.

Response: A sentence was added that highlights the originality of the work

Comment: Sentences to rephrased

- The most common species in Algeria, particularly in the Tebessa region (Benkhedim et al., 2023), and many countries in the world (Nebbak et al., 2022), is *Culex pipiens* (Diptera: Culicidae)

- Many plant essential oils have the potential to be larvicides sources because of their combinations of related phenols and monoterpenoids

- Furthermore, its impacts on morphometric parameters, on the nutrition reserves and histological structure of *Cx. pipiens* larvae were examined.

Response: We rephrased these sentences.

Comment: Please, write the sentence 'Lipids, carbohydrates, and proteins were extracted using the method of Shibko et al. (1967) and calculated as described previously by Hamaidia et al. (2018)'.

Instead

Lipids, carbohydrates, and Proteins were extracted using the method of Shibko et al. (1967) and calculated as described previously (Hamaidia et al., 2018).

Response: We replaced the sentence.

Comment: Please, put the authors at the end of the sentence 'These results are comparable to those noticed in the literature (Dadalioglu et al., 2004; Flamini et al., 2007; Dahak et al., 2014) with a few variations in the main compounds and in the percentage of their constituents'.

Response: we put the authors at the end of the sentence.

Comment: Results and discussion: Insecticidal activity

Sentence to rephrased: 'This oil exhibited an insecticidal activity as function as applied doses.'

Response: We rephrased the sentence: This EO exhibited larvicidal activity, which increased as a function of concentration.

Comment: Effect of EO on morphometric parameters

Please; write 'day or days' instead 'd'.

Response: we replaced 'd' by 'day or days'

Comment: The sentence is unclear and should be rephrased 'This indicates that certain bioactive substances that function as insect growth regulators (IGRs) and likely have properties similar to juvenile hormone (JH) have certainly affected the endocrine regulation of metamorphosis and molting (Kabir et al., 2013)'.

Response: We have rephrased the sentence: This indicates that certain bioactive components in the essential oil likely disrupted the hormonal control of molting and metamorphosis, functioning as insect growth regulators (IGRs) with properties similar to juvenile hormone analogs (JHAs).

Comment: Effects of EO on biochemical profile: Please, write 'day or days' instead 'd' .

Response: we replaced 'd' by 'day or days'

Comment: Sentence to rephrased: 'Our results generally in accordance with those published by El-Maghraby et al. (2023) and Ahmed et al. (2022)'.

Response: This sentence is deleted.

Comment: Effect on the histological structure of the larvae

Figure 5. Malpighian tubules in Cx. pipiens larva: A) Control; B) LC25 treated larva; C) LC25 treated larva. C: cytoplasm; MT: Malpighian tubule; N: Nucleus. C) should be LC50

Response: Yes C) is LC50